

**АБЫЛАЙ ХАН АТЫНДАҒЫ ҚАЗАҚ ХАЛЫҚАРАЛЫҚ ҚАТЫНАСТАР
ЖӘНЕ ӘЛЕМ ТІЛДЕРІ УНИВЕРСИТЕТІ
КАЗАХСКИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ И
МИРОВЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ ИМЕНИ АБЫЛАЙ ХАНА
KAZAKH ABLAI KHAN UNIVERSITY OF INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS
AND WORLD LANGUAGES**

**«Аударматану және филология саласындағы мәдениаралық қарым-
қатынас мәселелері»**

IX студенттік ғылыми-практикалық конференцияның мақалалар

ЖИНАҒЫ

СБОРНИК

**статей IX студенческой научно-практической конференции
«Вопросы межкультурной коммуникации
в переводоведении и филологии»**

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

**of the 9th student theoretical and practical conference
“The Issues of Intercultural Communication in Translation Studies and
Philology”**

Алматы 2023

УДК 81`25:80
ББК 81.2-5:80

*Рекомендовано к изданию решением Академического Совета Факультета Перевода и
Филологии КазУМОиМЯ им. Абылай хана
(Протокол №10 от 4.05.2023)*

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Сборник статей IX студенческой научно-практической конференции «Вопросы межкультурной коммуникации в переводоведении и филологии». Алматы, 24 апреля 2023/ под ред. Б.М. Мизамхан – Алматы: Абылай хан атындағы ҚХҚЖӘТУ, 2023. – 292 стр.

Сборник включает результаты научно-исследовательской работы студентов факультета перевода и филологии КазУМОиМЯ им. Абылай хана по двум основным направлениям: «Лингвокультурология и межкультурная коммуникация как интерпретационная платформа перевода» и «Когнитивные лингвокультурологические и прагма-функциональные аспекты современной лингвистики и литературоведения».

УДК 81`25:80
ББК 81.2-5:80

A. Muradyan considers the term blending as a process of forming a word in accordance with one of five formal models: the beginning of the first word and the second whole word, the first whole word and the end of the second word, two whole words, partially overlapping each other at the junction, the beginning of the first word and the end of the second word, a word or part of it is placed inside another source word [24, p.2]. *Example: Many people trying becoming **Instafamous***. In this example, the word **Instafamous** is formed by blending words: Instagram and famous. [Internet of Things . Scientific journal p.25].

In the course of my work, I came to the conclusion that neologisms are quite common in scientific journals. They can be used in a variety of ways. Some analyzed neologisms tend to strive for brevity of form, the minimum expenditure of linguistic means for expressing thoughts. Thus, they perform the function of saving lexical means, due to which they attract attention and are easily memorized, therefore, they are spread more rapidly and are more often used in speech. I noted the fact that scientific and technological progress primarily contributes to the replenishment of the vocabulary of the English language, therefore neologisms related to the information and communication sphere are undoubtedly relevant and are increasingly found in speech. Obviously, the Internet is an inexhaustible source of new words in the language. New types of technologies, as well as social networks, are constantly emerging.

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УДК 81-139

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РУССКАЯ И АНГЛИЙСКАЯ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЯ ЧЕРЕЗ КУЛЬТУРНЫЕ ПРИНЦИПЫ КОНЦЕПТУАЛИЗАЦИИ

В данной статье приведен анализ фразеологических единиц и мировоззрения русской и английской культур, а также их семантическое сходство и структурные различия. Целью исследования является определение функции фразеологии в когнитивной лингвистике. На примере концепта "труд" приведен анализ фразеологических единиц русского и английского языков, а также их употребление в устной и письменной речи, а также наличие или отсутствие эквивалентов. Концептуализация национального видения анализируется в соответствии с семантическими и историческими особенностями употребления и их происхождения.

Ключевые слова: фразеологизмы, концептуализация, концептосфера, периферия, картина мира, культурное восприятие.

RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGY THROUGH CULTURAL PRINCIPLES OF CONCEPTUALIZATION

This article analyzes phraseological units and the worldview of Russian and English cultures, as well as their semantic similarities and structural differences. The purpose of the study is to identify the function of phraseology in cognitive linguistics. On the example of the concept "labour" is given an analyze of Russian and English phraseological units and their use in oral and written speech, as well as the presence or absence of their equivalents. The conceptualization of the national vision is analyzed according to the semantic and historical features of use.

Keywords: phraseological units, conceptualization, conceptsphere, periphery, picture of the world, cultural perception.

The analysis of the cognitive approach to the meaning of phraseological units for the Russian and English cultural picture of the world and their perception were carried out on the basis of more than 100 phraseological units. Cultural perception of the concepts greatly demonstrates the process of use of a foreign language for non-native speakers, therefore non-native speakers can familiarize themselves with systematized techniques for effective communication. Various concepts carry a socio-cultural content, which is an integral associative national attribute. Such concepts may also express a picture of the world in economic, geographical, folkloric, artistic, domestic senses and more. In this case, it is important to note that the concept may not have any equivalent in the representatives of the other inclination, unless it has a directly-opposite semantic content.

The key associations for entire generations become the key to the emergence of this concept in the everyday life of a certain age group of the Russian and English people. Phraseological units themselves are generally considered to express folk wisdom in the briefest form, a kind of reflection of observations and experiences of generations. V.N. Teliya points out that the phraseology can be defined from the position of a language-phenomenon, situationally denoting all types of information when conceptualized in the form of a "package, ready to be used as a text within a text". [1, p.8]. Cognitive phraseology studies the mental processes that ensure the storage, recall from memory of phraseological units in the perception of language and practical use in speech. In cognitive linguistics, phraseology is understood as stable, reproducible figures of speech, which are processed as lexemes and are characterized by their linguistic irregularity and national-historical background. Concepts may be expressed through proper names and their derivatives, historicisms, archaisms, literature images and geographical names.

As it is pointed by N.B. Saporova, the concept is studied from the perspective of the way a representative of a particular culture is oriented in the world around it, in the ability of a person to distinguish individual objects, both mental and material, in connection with the principles of national-cultural thinking [2, p.214-216]. The absence of an analogue of the cultural concept is inherently a source of misunderstanding, as well as forming a cultural and language barrier that makes communication more complicated. It means that, besides non-equivalent concepts, even if there are corresponding concepts in the interaction of national conceptspheres, the formal side of the linguistic picture of the world and its linguistic structure does not allow to transform a concept from one conceptsphere to another in the exact same volume [3, p.35].

From the perspective of cognitive linguistics, phraseology directly portrays linguistic consciousness and implies a complex source of information about national mentality, which has developed from four components that form the conceptualization:

1. Ethnic consciousness
2. Linguistic consciousness
3. Cultural consciousness
4. Religious consciousness

For the topic under discussion, the equivalence of concepts and phraseological units that reflect the national picture of the world of Russian and English people is of interest. The ability to translate certain expression (literally/loosely/adequate/equivalent) is equal to the availability of this expression for representatives of another nation. With the help of phraseological expressions that are not translated verbatim, but are perceived reinterpreted, the ethnic and non-widespread aspect of the language is enhanced. The phraseology reflects generational experience about every concept and word, therefore the figurative system of thinking of the people is original and unique, nationally specific. The structure of the conceptualization can be

studied on the example of proverbs, idioms and sayings as a perception of culturally different understandings of different values of the same object.

On the example of the conducted research of semantic groups of phraseology of the Russian and English languages, the classifications of which are based on the concept of "labour" are as follows:

1. The skill;
2. The time aspect;
3. The carelessness
4. The diligence;
5. The exhaustion;
6. The ineffectiveness;
7. The idleness and many others.

The following is a brief examination of each group, based on Russian and English phraseological dictionaries [4; 5; 6; 7; 8; 9].

1. The skill refers to a person's success in any fields of activity, accumulated through hard work and work in that activity. It can be noted in an idiom such as "a Jack of all trades" and its analogue "мастер на все руки". It refers to a person who can do a lot with his hands and work on his own. In Russian culture, the idiom is associated with the profession of glovemakers, who work in the field of sewing gloves for every hand of all materials and all parameters. In English culture, the origin of the mentioned above idiom dates back to the 14th century. At that time, the name Jack was generally used to describe an ordinary man. An example of this can be found in John Gower's Middle English poem "Confessio Amantis" (1390), - "A good felawe is Jacke".

On the other hand, the example of such an English proverb as "He works best who knows his trade." and its Russian analogue, "Дело мастера боится." This phraseological unit emphasises impeccable work in a particular field and usually acts as a praise/applause for a person who succeeds as a result of his labour. It is known that this proverb was present in Russian culture as early as the 19th century, so it was printed in a collection of proverbs by V. I. Dahl in 1862. It was published that at that time this expression had a second part, which hinted at the master who did not want to take up serious tasks and ended up stagnating: "...а иной мастер дела боится". In English culture, the true origins and records of use are unknown, but some have linked it to an allusion to a person who is well versed in trade and exchange market relations and able to secure a bargain for himself, labour in this context being linked to all the learning that led a person to the right to be considered a master of his trade.

2. The time aspect implies the duration during which labour is reproduced, for example, in the idiom "в час по чайной ложке" and the English equivalent "in dribs and drabs", which means they characterize work that goes very slowly and with frequent interruptions. The Russian version of the idiom is indigenous and not borrowed. Originally it had the meaning of methodically and regularity, where a teaspoon implies a small amount of action that in large numbers can pay off. I.V. Zakharenko notes the contrast of the concepts of an hour and a teaspoon as two different magnitudes of large and small volume. The English expression comes from the word "dribble", which implies "to go on little by little". According to the Oxford Dictionary of Phraseology, it is believed that one of the first uses of the idiom was as early as 1809 in a letter by governess Ellen Weston.

There is another example, "An oak is not felled at one stroke." and its Russian counterpart "И Москва не вдруг строилась." and "Little strokes fell great oaks." which in Russian culture is expressed as "Вода камень точит" All carry the meaning that behind every success story are years of systematic hard man-made work for one goal, motivating the worker that his perseverance and tenacity will pay off. For English speakers, these expressions were popularised thanks to Benjamin Franklin, who used them in "Poor Richard's Almanack". Russian analogues, on the other hand, came from chronicles of centuries of building the city, and the first records were as early as 1147. The expression for stubbornness and hard work was borrowed from the Latin "Gutta cavat lapidem".

3. The carelessness in labour can be noted in the expression "через пень-колоду", which in English is "by fits and starts", which share the meaning of working unevenly, inconveniently, badly. The Russian expression appeared among lumberjacks and had a comparative form, it was connected with walking over a stump, when stepping over a stump one can get into a rotten tree. And the English idiom was practiced in the early 17th century and is documented in a speech by the English theologian Robert Sanderson on the discontinuous and irregular pious life.

It is also worth noting the example of the Russian proverb "Горница хороша, да окна кривы", which has no actual English equivalent in modern language. This is because English culture is not very conversant with this concept, and the closest meaning would be expression "no use from the fool". This cultural difference can be explained by the fact that English culture has never been intimately familiar with such concepts that came from Russian culture. This proverb occurred because skillful construction of the home is associated with

intelligence, sensitivity, and human loving respect for one's home and labour. Therefore, if a house is made without effort, then it will not seem comfortable or ideal to a person who build it.

4. In contrast to the carelessness, the diligence in the concept of work is much richer in the periphery. For example, idioms such as "в поте лица", "засучив рукава", "с головой" in Russian and such as "work fingers to the bone", "pull socks up", "go to town" in English. They have both negative connotations, implying diligence harmful to one's own or others' health, and positive ones, referring to a full immersion in work in both cultures.

Using the example of the proverb "Дорогу осилит идущий." and the English equivalent "A journey of thousands of miles begins with a single step.", there are noticeable similarities not only in the message that in order to successfully complete the task you need to take it up and not throw it, but also similar verbatim. There is also a popular opinion that this phrase comes from Latin or from the ancient Roman interpretation of "Viam supervadet vadens", but in truth the proverb is originally Russian and first has been interpreted through the Indian "Rig Veda" into Latin, and therefore the interpretation of the English proverb is actually an analogue of Russian.

5. The exhausting and hard work is often expressed through idioms like "гнуть спину" and corresponding versions of this idiom in English "to work one's fingers to the bone". Labour is meant here by the fact that one may be engaged in work, therefore detrimental to one's well-being. The English expression is found as early as the early 18th century in the opera *The Beggar's Wedding* by Charles Coffee. Both phraseological expressions are transformed from the identification of the physical condition of the human body as a result of the process of labour activity, in the case of the back it implies load-lifting labour, in the case of the fingers it implies hyperbole on skin-wiping and smears.

Furthermore, using the expression "крутиться как белка в колесе", which comes from I.A. Krylov's fable "The Squirrel" (1833) and the English interpretation of "to be on the go", it can be seen that grueling work also implies a non-stop cyclical work that leads to exhaustion.

6. The futility of an activity in phraseology is usually expressed by examples of meaningless activities coming from fictional stories, for example: "Сизифов труд" or "бочка Данаид", but if speaking of phraseology that would express cultural influence, then the example "толочь воду в ступе" – "to thrash over old straw" can be identified. Both are based on the example of incomparable working conditions that lead not only to inconvenience but also to redundancy. It is believed that water was poured into a mortar by the wisemen who tried to enchant it, which is how the expression went from wasting effort and labour in vain for unattainable ends as well.

7. In many ways, phraseological units are recognised to condemn idleness in all cultures, while derivative interpretations encouraging inactivity appear later in a jocular manner. For example, idioms such as "бить баклуши" – "to twiddle one's thumbs", "валяться на боку" (derived from the word лежебока) – "idle away one's time" and "сидеть сложа руки" – "to sit on one's hands" have the same meaning. In spite of these there are also such Russian expressions as "работа дураков любит" and "работа не бей лежачего", which have no equivalent in English speech, except when the text is translated verbatim. It can be said that this is because the far periphery associated with labour in Russian is made up of the same-relative words. For instance, труд-трудно, работа-раб, служить-слуга.

Based on all of the above, it is possible to designate semantic and cognitive signs of labour activity in phraseology indicate that in Russian and English linguacultural work is significant for obtaining a quality product or award, temporary perception of the framework for work that needs to be done with a lot of effort. But at the same time, in Russian linguoculture, an associative series of stable signs of a negative nature about the concept is more common. The above analysis has revealed that the cultural concept can be predetermined through the consciousness components continuously involved in the life of national representatives: ethnic, linguistic, cultural and religious. Moreover, all of them are interconnected with phraseological concepts.

In Russian and English phraseology, concepts are presented as human experience, closely related to the sphere of activity and being of Russian and English cultures. Overall, it follows that the national consciousness and the picture of the world are saturated with universal concepts with different fields of periphery. This means that both languages exist together in the environment as complex systems that reflect the wisdom of the nations, their uniqueness and commonalities. On this basis, it can be stated that realities have changed, are changing, will continue to change, and must be considered in their relevance to the national picture of the world.

It can be underlined from the research that the etymological component is only a part of the historical component of the concepts in the linguistic picture of the world, because values can be reflected by various semantic groups per each concept. Concepts reflect cognitive and value approaches mastering reality and its moral assessment, each culture has a material or mental representation of them and in some cases, it can be differently distinct for both languages. A complete perception of a concept with the help of phraseology is

impossible, as the concept remains the result of the individual categorization of an individual and is an abstract structured unit, which cannot pretend to be an absolute speech representation in a linguistic analysis. It is also important to highlight that a significant indicator of accessibility to another culture of a concept is the possibility of its literal translation, as a rewriting of the basic cultural concept, which is expressed lexically through the perspective of another language allows denoting the degree of cultural influence on the concept by its accessibility to another culture and the ability to convey its meaning to non-native speakers of the language.

In particular, phraseological units are an indicator of familiarity, saturation and rich vocabulary of the speaker. Phraseological units contribute to the modeling of the world in human consciousness, act as explicators of prototypical categories of perception of reality and contribute to the modeling of the world in human consciousness, act as explicators of prototypical categories of perception of reality, because even being a set of concepts, they can elevate one specific concept in the core of its conceptosphere.

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УДК 81

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FEATURES OF SONG TRANSLATION

The article discusses such issues as the complexity of song translation, the peculiarities of song translation and provides examples of translation of songs in Spanish and French. The article concludes that the most convenient method of translation is to adapt the song and make variations of the author into the translation.

Keywords: features of translation, difficulties, methods, structure of songs

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ESPECIFICIDAD DE LA TRADUCCIÓN DEL DISCURSO DE LA CANCIÓN

El artículo analiza cuestiones como la complejidad de la traducción de canciones, las peculiaridades de la traducción de canciones y proporciona ejemplos de traducción de canciones en español y francés. El artículo

«Аударматану және филология саласындағы мәдениаралық қарым-қатынас мәселелері»
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ЖИНАҒЫ

СБОРНИК

статей IX студенческой научно-практической конференции
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в переводоведении и филологии»

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

of the 9th student theoretical and practical conference
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Издательство не несет ответственности за содержание авторских материалов
и не предоставляет гарантий в связи с публикацией фактов, данных, результатов и другой информации

Подписано в печать 18.05.2023 г.
Гарнитура «Times New Roman. MS Minsho»
Формат 70x90 1/8. Объем 36,5 п.л. Заказ №3288. Тираж 150 экз.
Сверстано и отпечатано в издательстве «Полилингва»
При КазУМОиМЯ имени Абылай хана

Издательство «Полилингва» КазУМОиМЯ имени Абылай хана
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